

PSSOH and Descon post-conference

“How to assemble Klimerko workshop”

Klimerko is DIY air quality measuring device that measures Particulate Matter in the air as well as Temperature, Humidity and Pressure. Purpose of this workshop is to introduce Klimerko (local open hardware project) to the participants, and after that to demonstrate how someone can assemble and install Klimerko at home.

17:00 – 17:30 Presentation about Klimerko and “Vazduh građanima” initiative
Desiree Željka Milošević, Vanja Stanić

17:30 – 18:30 Demonstration of assembling Klimerko
Vanja Stanić, Desiree Željka Milošević, Nikola Todorović

18:30 – 19:00 Q & A
Desiree Željka Milošević, Vanja Stanić

Language: Serbian

Date: October 31, 2020 (post-conference day)

Time: 17:00

Place: TBA, University of Belgrade – School of Electrical Engineering, Bulevar kralja Aleksandra 73, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia, URL: <http://pssoh.etf.bg.ac.rs/>, Contact: pssoh@etf.bg.ac.rs

Useful links: <http://klimerko.org/>, <https://github.com/DesconBelgrade/Klimerko>

PSSOHi Descon post-konferencijska

“Radionica kako napraviti Klimerka”

Klimerko je uređaj koji meri kvalitet vazduha tako što meri količinu PM čestica u vazuhu kao i temperaturu, vlažnost vazduha i pritisak. Cilj ove radionice je da sve učesnike upoznamo sa Klimerkom (lokalnim projektom otvorenog hardvera), a zatim da demonstriramo kako neko može sam da sastavi i postavi kod kuće Klimerka.

17:00-17:30 Prezentacija Klimerka i inicijative “Vazduh građanima”
Desiree Željka Milošević, Vanja Stanić

17:30 – 18:30 Demonstracija sastavljanja Klimerka
Vanja Stanić, Nikola Todorović

18:30 – 19:00 Pitanja & odgovori
Desiree Željka Milošević, Vanja Stanić

Jezik radionice: srpski

Datum: 31. oktobar, 2020 (post-konferencijski događaji)

Mesto: TBA, Univerzitet u Beogradu – Elektrotehnički fakultet, Bulevar kralja Aleksandra 73, 11000

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Korisni linkovi: <http://klimerko.org/>, <https://github.com/DesconBelgrade/Klimerko>